

A CONCEPTUAL STUDY OF SERVICE QUALITY, TOURIST SATISFACTION AND REVISIT INTENTION

DR. GOLDI PURI¹

ASSISTANT PROFESSOR INSTITUTE OF HOTEL AND TOURISM MANAGEMENT MAHARISHI
DAYANAND UNIVERSITY ROHTAK, HARYANA.
EMAIL: drgoldipuri@gmail.com.

KULDEEP SINGH²

RESEARCH SCHOLAR
INSTITUTE OF HOTEL AND TOURISM MANAGEMENT MAHARISHI DAYANAND UNIVERSITY
ROHTAK, HARYANA.
EMAIL: singh911kuldeep@gmail.com.

ABSTRACT

In marketing studies there is a close relationship between service quality, tourist satisfaction and revisit intention from so many years. It is to be noted that despite of vast number of literature available, there is still need to investigate these three dimensions theoretically. Therefore, judgment of quality by consumer should be given the highest priority and his decision regarding the quality of service should be welcome by the suppliers. There is not clarity between the concept of service quality and tourist satisfaction and revisit intention. The purpose of this paper is to understand the concept between them with the help of SERVQUAL Model. Many organizations played an important role to understand it and they mainly focus on the revisit intention of the tourist. This conceptual paper also highlights the management strategies in tourism industry with future implication.

KEYWORDS: Service Quality, Tourist Satisfaction, Revisit Intention, SERVQUAL, Tourism.

1 Introduction

There are several reasons for the expansion of tourism sector .It is due to convenient transportation between countries that encouraged a growth in tourism and the people from various nations are more comfortable to travel in other foreign country. Jonsson Kvist (2005) revealed that changes in demography played an important role which also includes the grey tourists with a larger section of elder people who are comparatively wealthy as compared to younger tourists who are more like backpackers. Many researchers argue that service quality, tourist satisfaction and revisit intention become an essential dimension for the growth of service providers. Service quality can have positive impact on tourist satisfaction and it also leads to revisit intention.

1.1 Meaning of Quality

There are various definitions of Quality; one of the popular definitions of quality is that it refers to the “*totality of features and characteristics of a product or service that bear on its ability to satisfy given needs*”. The recent notion of quality is ‘fitness for purpose’. This new idea moves the assessment of quality from the service provider to the buyer.

Phillips et al. (1983) and Anderson & Zeithmal (1984) argued in their research that due to advantage of high quality service, profits in the industry also increases which in turn improve productivity. Rabin (1983) described that during the period of 1980 ‘*quality*’ played a significant role in service industry. Takeuchi and Quelch (1983) confirmed that tourists are more aware about the better quality in their services.

1.2 Characteristics of Quality

Crosby (1979) declared that the meaning of quality is misguided as “*goodness, or luxury, or shininess, or weight.*” It is not easy for consumers to express the need of quality (Takeuchi & Quelch, 1983). Monroe and Krishnan (1983) pointed out that researchers face problem while evaluating quality. Researchers like Phillips et al. (1983) verified the advantages of quality that increase market share. Several researchers like (Bateson, 1977; Berry, 1980; Lovelock, 1981; & Shostak, 1977) argued that services are intangible in nature According to Booms and Bitner (1981) it is difficult to measure uniformity of behavior because there is a gap between delivery of services and experienced services.

2 Review of Literature

Crosby (1979) was one of the principal scholars who studied the evaluation of quality and found high accuracy in his findings. Parsuraman et al. (1988) initiated the work which was focus on service and after that many studies on service quality have been investigated in many fields like insurance, healthcares, banks, hospitals, government services, cellular services, IT services, marketing, library sciences, travel & tourism and retail sector (Babakus & Mangold, 1992; Curry, 1999; Duncan & Elliot, 2002; Gagliano & Hathcote, 1994; Nwankwo & Richardson, 1994; & Sureshchandar et al.; 2001, 2002).

Parasuraman et al. (1985) described ‘*service quality*’ as “*the degree and direction of discrepancy between customer’s perceptions and expectations*”. Also they described “*perceived service quality*” as “*the gap between customers` expectations and perceptions*”. They also argued that if there is less error in services and the difference among ‘*expectation*’ and ‘*perception*’ of consumer is less, it will enhance customer satisfaction.

2.1 Existing Understanding of Service Quality

Many researchers have investigated the research on service quality (Gronroos, 1982; Lehtinen & Lehtinen, 1982; Lewis and Booms, 1983; Olsen & Wyckoff, 1978). Lehtinen and Lehtinen (1982) claimed that “*service quality is delivered when there is the interaction between a customer and the service*”. Service quality has been an essential topic of study connecting tourism & management departments. Though, a substantial quantity of research on quality of

services, the purpose behind intention of revisit a destination along with what is the requirement of superior quality service from the tourism department has to be answered (Puri & Singh, 2018).

Types of quality

According to Gronroos (1982) there are 2 two aspects of service quality:

- (1) **Technical quality:** It refers to “what the consumer is actually receiving from the service”.
- (2) **Functional quality:** It refers to “how *the service is delivered*”.

In service industry the “what” i.e.’ technical quality’ are more complicated to estimate. For instance, in medical services it is not easy for customers to measured service quality pre and post treatments. Due to this factor, customers and buyers shifted to some others attributes of quality which are related to the process of medical services i.e. known ‘*how*’ also called ‘*functional quality*’. As a result, consumers depend on other aspects of services like empathy and reliability.

Table 1 Concept of Service Quality

Source	Concept of Service Quality
Lewis & Booms (1983)	“Service quality is a measure of how well the service level delivered matches customer expectations”.
Parasuraman et al. (1988)	“Global judgment or attitude relating to the superiority of the service”.
Zeithaml (1988)	“Customers’ assessment of the overall excellence or superiority of the service”.
Gronroos (1990)	“The outcome of an evaluation process involving customers’ comparison of their expectations and experiences”.
Asubonteng et al. (1996)	“The difference between customers’ expectations of service performance prior to the service encounter and their perceptions of the service perceived”.

Source (Roostika, 2009)

2.2 Attributes of Service Quality

There are six criteria of perceived service quality according to Grönroos (1990) i.e. skills and professionalism, accessibility and flexibility, behavior and attitudes; trustworthiness and ability, reputation, recovery and credibility. According to Berry et al. (1985) reliability is the most important variable that leads to customer satisfaction. Gilbert and Wong (2003) claimed that there are seven variables for evaluating services in airline industry: Customization, Reliability, flight patterns, facilities, responsiveness, employees and assurance.

According to Hudson et al. (2004) service quality in the tourism industry receives growing consideration and most of the studies in tourism applied the device named (SERVQUAL) which helps to evaluate the service quality.

3 Research Methodology

This paper is conceptual in nature and based on mainly secondary data derived from various literature sources includes diverse research articles, book chapters, reports, news articles, and websites. In addition, this paper carries out the effect of discussion with tourist, service providers and officials'. The researcher also used information and facts already available as base in order to analyze, explore and evaluate the problem at hand critically to figure out conclusion.

4 Focus of the Paper

The main focus purpose of the paper is to understand the meaning of service quality, satisfaction and revisit intention through SERVQUAL Model and other factors. Specifically, this study highlights the attributes of these three dimensions on the basis of previous studies of the researchers. Some future directions with management strategies also discussed in this study.

5 Overview of SERVQUAL

The idea of SERVQUAL model was formulated by Parasuraman et al. (1985) where they defined the concept of service quality "*as the degree of discrepancy between a customer's normative expectation of a service and his or her perceptions of service performance.*" According to Brysland and Curry (2001) this model is very useful in the service industry and can be verified for yardstick use.

Parasuraman et al (1988) initiated the model called SERVQUAL that includes the twenty two items which assessed the five important factors called, **assurance, responsiveness, empathy, tangibles and reliability**. This model mainly focuses on the key areas and gives freedom for researchers to instigate that the dimension of SERVQUAL allows researchers to uncover the important issues regarding the concept of service quality and their variables.

Decades of research have investigated about the application of ‘SERVQUAL’ model in service industry. It is to be assumed to be one of the reliable instruments that applied in diverse service sectors. Many researchers applied in the health care sectors .Some of the scholars who applied the SERVQUAL instrument like in health services are **(Babakus & Mangold; 1992; Bowers et al., 1994; Clow et al., 1995; Lytle & Mokwa, 1992; Woodside et al., 1989)**. Likewise, some other researchers like **Carman (1990) and McAlexander et al. (1994)** applied this instrument in dental care services. It is also applied in retail services; dry cleaning, banking, pest control and restaurants services **(Cronin & Taylor, 1992; Teas, 1993)**.

5.1 Qualitative Use of SERVQUAL

It is to be noted that SERVQUAL can help the service providers after giving the information regarding the customer’s judgment about the quality of the services. There are some categories of service quality like ‘responsiveness’ and ‘reliability’ which help the consumers to judge their quality. Also, many consumers judge their service quality with the performance level according to their thinking and expectations before services. Furthermore, the quality of service can be measured after comparing the expectations of consumers with perception. If the performance of the service provider is lower than the expectations than it will leads to lower service quality .According to many scholars it may be applied in any industry .For this purpose quality of service can be evaluated after comparison of ‘expectations’ and ‘perceptions’ of consumers and the information from customers can be taken about the services delivered. There are many sources of communication like complaints from customers, feedback from service providers and word of mouth communication.

5.2 Quantitative Use of SERVQUAL

There are following steps while using the SERVQUAL in a quantitative way:

- (1) To focus on the various aspects of “service quality “and to identified them.
- (2) To evaluate the expectations and performance of customers.
- (3) To compare the expectations with perception and to analyze the opportunities and threats in the study of service quality.
- (4) To focus on the improvement and to minimize the shortcomings and maximize the opportunities.

5.3 Criticism

According to Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry (1994) there are three dimensions instead of five dimensions i.e. tangible, reliability and a single factor for empathy, assurance and responsiveness. Brady and Cronin (2001) in their study argued that service quality focus on the third order factor model: interaction, environment quality and outcome. The importance for

measuring perceived service quality is recognized by many authors like (Carman 1990; Koelemeijer 1991; Fick and Ritchie 1991; McDougall and Levesque 1992).

Carman (1990) argued that few of these attributes of service quality are not reliable as compared to other service industries. Also, Carman (1990) criticized the SERVQUAL model of Parsuraman et al. (1988) and indicates the fault of validity of SERVQUAL scale. According to him 22 attributes of SERVQUAL scale are not consistent and not applied in the service industry.

Further, Sureshchandar et al. (2001) indicated that this model faced huge criticism from many researchers for several reasons and it become famous due to its capability to forecast service quality in universal way. As a result, this instrument becomes one of the cornerstones in tourism industry to measure service quality from customers' point of view.

6 Understanding Satisfaction

Satisfaction is an imperative component to maintain long-term relationships with customers. Sureschandar et al. (2002) claimed that customer satisfaction can occur at multiple levels in and organization such as satisfaction with the 'contact person, core service or the organization as a whole'. From many studies it is revealed that the satisfaction of customers merged with the Gronroos and SERVQUAL model. There are many variables like functional quality, technical quality, perceived price, service quality, corporate image and internal and external influence. The variables have a positive effect on customer's satisfaction in the service sector.

On the basis of level of reinforcement and degree of arousal he defined '*satisfaction-as-contentment*', '*satisfaction-as-pleasure*', '*satisfaction-as-relief*', '*satisfaction-as-novelty*' and '*satisfaction-as-surprise*'.

6.1 Disconfirmation

This definition introduced the model named as 'disconfirmation of expectations paradigm'. Oliver (1980) formulated the three determinants of customer satisfaction i.e. **expectations, perceptions and disconfirmation**. The Disconfirmation is the outcome of a 'discrepancy between expectations and perceptions'. There are 2 types of disconfirmation i.e.: (1) positive disconfirmation occurs when product performance exceeds prior expectations and (2) negative disconfirmation occurs when expectations exceed performance. Therefore the positive disconfirmation will leads to customer satisfaction, on the other hand negative disconfirmation will leads to dissatisfaction.

According to Churchill and Surprenant (1982), Woodruff et al. (1983) & Oliver and DeSarbo (1988) product or performance from the service have a direct effect on satisfaction .At last Oliver

(1993) stated that “there is no direct relation between expectations and satisfaction as the effect of expectations is totally mediated by disconfirmation.

6.2 Customer Satisfaction

Kotler (2012) defined customer satisfaction “*as the level of one's feelings after comparing perceived performance or results compared with expectations*”.

Consumer satisfaction as a condition where consumer needs, wants, and expectations can be met through consumed products” (Gasperz, 2002).

To measure customer satisfaction there are following indicators:

- a. Safe & Secure Transaction & Quality of Services.
- b. Friendly Behavior from service providers.
- c. Sellers mastery while selling products and convincing skill, so that consumers buy them.
- d. Responsiveness while handling complaints of consumers.
- e. Politeness of service providers.
- f. Visual appearance of building and cleanliness.

6.3 Understanding Tourist Satisfaction

Chen and Tsai (2007) defined “*tourist satisfaction as a positive perception or feeling that tourists develop or acquire by engaging in recreational activities and is expressed as the degree of pleasure derived from such experiences*”. In tourism industry, satisfaction of tourist is very important as it has direct effect on the destination choice.

6.4 Relationship between Service Quality And Satisfaction

Notable researchers like Parasuraman et al. (1988) & Bolton and Drew (1991) claimed that “*concept of service quality as a ‘form of attitude*”. They argued that it is different from satisfaction but also interrelated. According to them satisfaction can be formed after assessment of expectations of consumer and their perception. There are different views from several researchers like (Parasuraman et al., 1994; Dabholkar, 1995; Sureshchandar et al., 2002) regarding service quality and customer satisfaction but they are also interrelated. Narayan et al. (2007) investigated the dimensions like service quality and tourist satisfaction in their studies. Adinegara (2018) in their study examined the role of quality of services in hotels and destination, word of mouth, intention to revisit and hotel image on tourist satisfaction in Bali.

6.5 Different Views of Both Dimensions

There is general consensus about some disagreements regarding the theory of both ‘service quality’ and ‘customer satisfaction’ in service sector. There are two different theories that have different view regarding these two dimensions. Scholars like Woodside *et al.* (1989) supported the theory that service quality leads to customer satisfaction. On the other hand Bitner (1990)

argued that customer satisfaction leads to service quality. Some others scholars like Bowers *et al.* (1994) suggested that satisfaction and quality are interrelated and similar in characteristic. Word of mouth is an important element of service quality claimed by (Bowers *et al.*, 1994; Reidenbach & Sandifer-Smallwood, 1990).

7 Understanding Revisit Intention

According to **Kozak (2001)** *“Tourist revisit intention is an actual response to certain behaviours which generally refers to the tourist willingness to visit a certain destinations or other destinations in the same country”*.

Seetanaiah *et al.* (2020) analyzed the satisfaction of tourist and their relationship with service quality of airport at destinations and revisit intention.

According to Li *et al.* (2008) many scholars from tourism industry described tourism as a “search for novel experiences that are distinct from the routine experiences encountered at home”. Some tourists prefer the home friendly atmosphere when they travelled outside their usual place for vacations. According to Beck (1992) & Rojek (2000) tourist’s safety and security are very essential in the modern world. Li *et al.* (2008) also revealed that tourist who like to revisit a destination enjoy their vacation for artistic and function reasons and feel more comfortable in that place as he is already aware of its environment.

7.1 Behavioral Intention

According to Chang *et al.* (2014) in tourism industry it is essential to recognize the behavioral intentions and purchase behavior of tourists. Zhang *et al.* (2014) & Wang (2004) recommended that repeat tourists likes to pay more money and stay for a longer duration. Swan (1981) defined *“behavioral intention as an individual’s probable or pre arranged future behavior and can be examined in terms of fixed behaviors.”* Lam and Hsu’s (2006) investigated perceived behavioral control and attitude which have a positive effect on behavioral intention in Hong Kong as attraction .Many scholars have described behavior of tourists as one-dimensional .Chen (2008) studied two items i.e. recommended intention and repurchase intention to evaluate passengers revisit intention in airline industry.

8 Conclusion and Future Implication

This conceptual paper highlighted the three dimensions i.e. service quality, tourist satisfaction and revisit intention. It is important to understand the theoretical concept between service quality and tourist satisfaction .It can be achieved after the improvement in service quality. As there is no single accepted definition of service quality, various views of researchers from previous studies discussed in this paper .This paper also highlighted the overview of SERVQUAL model

and their qualitative and quantitative use. Researcher also focused on the criticism of the SERVQUAL. The concept of satisfaction and attributes also discussed in this paper. At last, meaning of revisit intention and concept of behavioral intention have been discussed.

It is to be noted that to manage perceived service quality, satisfaction of tourist is very important which influence revisit intention. This can be done by matching the expected and perceived services. In addition, further investigation is needed to fill the gap between service quality, tourist satisfaction and revisit intention. For this purpose, the role of managers is very critical to understand these three dimensions to attract more tourists in future.

References

- Adinegara, J., Suprpti, N. W. S., Yasa, N. N. K., & Sukaatmadja, I. (2018). Antecedents And Consequences Of Tourist Satisfaction: A Literature Review. *ASEAN Marketing Journal*, 40-53.
- Anderson, Carl and Carl P. Zeithaml (1984), "Stage of the Product Life Cycle, Business Strategy, and Business Performance," *Academy of Management Journal*, 27 (March), 5-24.
- Asubonteng, P, McCleary, KJ & Swan, JE 1996, 'SERVQUAL revisited: a critical review of service quality', *The Journal of Services Marketing*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 62-81.
- Babakus, E. & Mangold, G.W. (1992), "Adapting the SERVQUAL Scale to Hospital Services: An Empirical Investigation", *Health Services Research*, 26 (6): 767-86
- Bateson, John E. G. (1977), "Do We Need Service Marketing?," in *Marketing Consumer Services: New Insights*, Cambridge, MA: Marketing Science Institute, Report #77- 115
- Beck, U. (1992). *Risk society*, trans. M. Ritter.
- Berry, Leonard L. (1980), "Services Marketing Is Different," *Business*, 30 (May-June), 24-28.
- Bitner, M.J. (1990), "Evaluating service encounters: the effects of physical surroundings and employee responses", *Journal of Marketing*, Vol. 54 No. 4, pp. 69-82
- Bolton, R. N., & Drew, J. H. (1991). A multistage model of customers' assessments of service quality and value. *Journal of consumer research*, 17(4), 375-384.
- Booms, Bernard H. and Mary J. Bitner (1981), "Marketing Strategies and Organization Structures for Services Firms," in *Marketing of Services*, J. Donnelly and W. George, eds., Chicago: American Marketing, 4

Bowers, M.R., Swan, J.E. and Koehler, W.F. (1994), "What attributes determine quality and satisfaction with health care delivery?", *Health Care Management Review*, Vol. 19 No. 4, pp. 49-55.

Brady, M. K., & Cronin Jr, J. J. (2001). Some new thoughts on conceptualizing perceived service quality: a hierarchical approach. *Journal of marketing*, 65(3), 34-49.

Bryslund, A., & Curry, A. (2001). Service improvements in public services using SERVQUAL. *Managing Service Quality*, 11, 389-401

Carman, J.M. (1990), "Consumer perceptions of service quality: an assessment of the SERVQUAL dimensions", *Journal of Retailing*, Vol. 66 No. 1, pp. 33-55.

Chang, -L.-L., Backman, K. F., & Huang, Y. C. (2014). Creative tourism: A preliminary examination of creative tourists' motivation, experience, perceived value and revisit intention. *International Journal of Culture, Tourism and Hospitality Research*, 8(4), 401–419.

Chen, C.-F. (2008). Investigating structural relationships between service quality, perceived value, satisfaction, and revisit intention for air passengers: Evidence from Taiwan. *Transportation Research Part A*, 42, 709–717

Chen, C., & Tsai, D. (2007). How destination image and evaluative factors affect behavioral intentions. *Tourism Management*, 28(4), 1115-1122.

Churchill Jr, G. A., & Surprenant, C. (1982). An investigation into the determinants of customer satisfaction. *Journal of marketing research*, 19(4), 491-504.

Clow, K. E., Fischer, A. K. and O'Bryan, D. (1995),. "Patient expectations of dental services", *Journal of Health Care Marketing*, Vol. 15 No. 3, pp. 23-31

Cronin, J.J. and Taylor, S.A. (1992), "Measuring service quality: a reexamination and extension", *Journal of Marketing*, Vol. 56, July, pp. 55-68.

Crosby, Philip B. (1979), *Quality Is Free: The Art of Making Quality Certain*, New York: New American Lib

Curry, A. (1999), "Innovation in Public Service Management", *Managing Service Quality*, 9 (3): 180-90

Dabholkar, P. A. (1995). A contingency framework for predicting causality between customer satisfaction and service quality. *ACR North American Advances*.

Duncan, E. Elliott (2002), "Customer Service Quality and Financial Performance among Australian Retail Financial Institutions" *Journal of Financial Services Marketing*," 7 (1): 25-41.

Fick, G. R., & Ritchie, J. R. (1991). Measuring service quality in the travel and tourism industry. *Journal of Travel Research*, 30(2), 2-9.

Gagliano, K.B. & Hathcote, J. (1994), "Customer Expectations and Perceptions of Service Quality in Apparel Retailing", *Journal of Services Marketing*, 8(1): 60-9

Gilbert, D., & Wong, R. K. (2003). Passenger expectations and airline services: a Hong Kong based study. *Tourism Management*, 24(5), 519-532.

Gronroos, Christian (1978), "A Service-Oriented Approach to Marketing of Services," *European Journal of Marketing*, 12 (no. 8), 588-601. (1982), *Strategic Management and Marketing in the Service Sector*, Helsingfors: Swedish School of Economics and Business Administration.

Gaspersz, V. (2002). Pedomian implementasi program six sigma terintegrasi dengan ISO 9001: 2000, MBNQA, dan HACCP. *PT. Gramedia Pustaka Utama, Jakarta*.

Gronroos, C 1990, *Service management and marketing: managing the moments in truth in service competition*, Lexington Books, Lexington, MA.

Hudson S, Hudson P, Miller GA. 2004. The measurement of service quality in the tour operating sector: a methodological comparison. *Journal of Travel Research* 42: 305–312.

Koelemeijer, K. (1991). Perceived customer service quality: issues on theory and measurement. In *Proc. 6th World Conf. Research in the distributive trades, The Hague, The Netherlands* (pp. 68-76).

Kotler, P. (2012). *Kotler on marketing*. Simon and Schuster.

Kozak, M. (2001), "Repeaters' behavior at two distinct destinations", *Annals of Tourism Research*, Vol. 28 No. 3, pp. 784-807.

Kvist, A. K. J. (2005). Needs and Expectations of Inbound Tourists Visiting a Peripheral Area. *Luleå, Licentiate Thesis*, 7

Lam, T., & Hsu, C. H. C. (2006). Predicting behavioral intention of choosing a travel destination. *Tourism Management*, 27, 589–599.

Lehtinen, Uolevi and Jarmo R. Lehtinen (1982), "Service Quality: A Study of Quality Dimensions," unpublished working paper, Helsinki: Service Management Institute, Finland OY.

Lewis, Robert C. and Bernard H. Booms (1983), "The Marketing Aspects of Service Quality," in *Emerging Perspectives on Services Marketing*, L. Berry, G. Shostack, and G. Upah, eds., Chicago: American Marketing, 99-

Li, X., Cheng, C.-K., Kim, H. and Petrick, J. (2008), "A systematic comparison of first-time and repeat visitors via a two-phase survey", *Tourism Management*, Vol. 29, pp. 278-93.

Lovelock, Christopher H. (1980), "Towards a Classification of Services," in *Theoretical Developments in Marketing*, C. Lamb and P. Dunne, eds., Chicago: American Marketing, 72-76.

Lytle, R.S. and Mokwa, M.P. (1992), "Evaluating health care quality: the moderating role of outcomes", *Journal of Health Care Marketing*, Vol. 12 No. 1, pp. 4-14

McAlexander, J.H., Kaldenberg, D.O. and Koenig, H.F. (1994), "Service quality measurement: examination of dental practices sheds more light on the relationships between service quality, satisfaction, and purchase intentions in a health care setting", *Journal of Health Care Marketing*, Vol. 14 No. 3, pp. 34-40.

McDougall, G. H., & Levesque, T. (2000). Customer satisfaction with services: putting perceived value into the equation. *Journal of services marketing*.

Monroe, Kent B. and R. Krishnan (1983), "The Effect of Price on Subjective Product Evaluations," Blacksburg: Virginia Polytechnic Institute, working

Narayan, B., Rajendran, C., Sai, L. P., & Gopalan, R. (2009). Dimensions of service quality in tourism—an Indian perspective. *Total Quality Management*, 20(1), 61-89.

Nwankwo, S. & Richardson, B. (1994), "Measuring and Achieving Quality Customer Service in the Public Sector",

Oliver, R. L. (1980). A cognitive model of the antecedents and consequences of satisfaction decisions. *Journal of marketing research*, 17(4), 460-469.

Oliver, R. L., & DeSarbo, W. S. (1988). Response determinants in satisfaction judgments. *Journal of consumer research*, 14(4), 495-507.

Parasuraman, A., Zeithami, V. & Berry L. L. (1985), "A Conceptual Model of Service Quality and Its Implications for Future Research", *Journal of Marketing*, 49 (Fall): 41-50.

Parasuraman, A., Zeithami, V. & Berry, L.L. (1988), "SERVQUAL: a Multiple Item Scale for Measuring Consumer Perceptions of Quality", *Journal of Retailing*, 64 (1): 12-40.

Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, V. A., & Berry, L. L. (1994). Reassessment of expectations as a comparison standard in measuring service quality: implications for further research. *Journal of marketing*, 58(1), 111-124.

Phillips, Lynn W., Dae R. Chang, and Robert D. Buzzell (1983), "Product Quality, Cost Position, and Business Performance: A Test of Some Key Hypotheses," *Journal of Marketing*, 47 (Spring),

Puri, G., & Singh, K. (2018). The Role of Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction in Tourism Industry: A Review of Servqual Model. *IJRAR-International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews*, 5(4), 745-751.

Rabin, Joseph H. (1983), "Accent Is on Quality in Consumer Services This Decade," *Marketing News*, 17 (March 4), 12.

Reidenbach, E.R. and Sandifer-Smallwood, B. (1990), "Exploring perceptions of hospital operations by a modified SERVQUAL approach", *Journal of Health Care Marketing*, Vol. 10 No. 4, pp. 47-55

Roostika, R. (2009). *The Role of Customer Value within the Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction and Behavioural Intentions Relationships: An Empirical Examination in the Indonesian Higher Education Sector*.

Rojek, C. (2000), *Leisure and Culture*, MacMillan Press, London.

Rust, R. T., & Oliver, R. L. (Eds.). (1993). *Service quality: New directions in theory and practice*. Sage Publications

Sasser, W. E., Olsen, R. P., & Wyckoff, D. D. (1978). *Management of service operations: Text, cases, and readings*. Allyn & Bacon.

Seetanah, B., Teeroovengadam, V., & Nunkoo, R. (2020). Destination satisfaction and revisit intention of tourists: does the quality of airport services matter?. *Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Research*, 44(1), 134-148.

Shostack, G. Lynn (1977), "Breaking Free from Product Marketing," *Journal of Marketing*, 41 (April), 73-80

Sureshchandar, G.S., Rajendran, C, & Anantharaman, R.N. (2001), "The Relationship between Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction-a Factor Specific Approach", *Journal of Services Marketing*, 16 (4): 363-79

Sureshchandar, G.S., Rajendran, C, Anantharaman R.N., & Kamalanabhan, T.J. (2002), "Management's Perception of Total Quality Service in the Banking Sector of a Developing Economy - a Critical Analysis", *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 20 (4): 181-96

Swan, J. (1981). Disconfirmation of expectations and satisfaction with a retail service. *Journal of Retailing*, 57(3), 49–66

Takeuchi, Hirotaka and John A. Quelch (1983), "Quality Is More Than Making a Good Product," *Harvard Business Review*, 61 (July-August), 139

Teas, K.R. (1993), "Expectations, performance evaluation, and consumers' perceptions of quality", *Journal of Marketing*, Vol. 57, October, pp. 18-34.

Wang, D. (2004). Tourist behaviour and repeat visitation to Hong Kong. *Tourism Geographies*, 6 (1), 99–118

Woodruff, R. B., Cadotte, E. R., & Jenkins, R. L. (1983). Modeling consumer satisfaction processes using experience-based norms. *Journal of marketing research*, 20(3), 296-304.

Woodside, A.G., Frey, L.L. and Daly, R.T. (1989), "Linking service quality, customer satisfaction", *Journal of Health Care Marketing*, December, pp. 5-17.

Zeithaml, VA 1988, 'Consumer perceptions of price, quality and value: a means-end model and synthesis of evidence', *Journal of Marketing*, vol. 52, no. 3, pp. 2-22.

Zhang, H., Fu, X., Cai, L. A., & Lu, L. (2014). Destination image and tourist loyalty: A metaanalysis. *Tourism Management*, 40, 213–223.